

CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS.

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INTRODUCTION

Today, training of qualified specialists and improving the quality of education using electronic educational resources is one of the urgent issues.

In order to find a solution to these problems and fulfill the assigned tasks, the issues of further improvement of the education system by comprehensive analysis of the existing education system, complete elimination of existing problems and shortcomings, and effective use of advanced foreign experiences were put forward.

The capabilities of modern information and communication technologies are a very wide system, which includes a number of new concepts in addition to the known computer, multimedia tools, computer networks, and the Internet. To these information systems, information systems management, information transmission systems, data warehouse, information warehouse management systems, knowledge warehouse etc example to be possible

« Information technologies in the field education system more improvement, scientific research development and IT industry them with integration to do measures about »gi decisions and this to the activity belongs to that's it such as another regulatory and legal in the documents defined tasks done increases.

CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS.

H5P interactive elements. The H5P service (www.h5p.org) is a convenient and simple constructor that can be used to create interactive content for the educational process. To do this, the user creates his own interactive content by choosing any available template in the constructor. Interactive content can be embedded into a series of LMS or web pages using the embedding code provided by the builder.

Today, all H5P components are created in the modern HTML5 format, with the addition of JavaScript code and CSS styles. This allows the user to easily study the materials created using the corresponding service on any device and software.

Interactive content created in the constructor can be divided into the following categories:

- Game form (Games);
- Multimedia form (Multimedia);
- Question form (Questions).

More than 10 elements (text, image, table, reference, test, etc.) can be placed and managed in the content of interactive video content to strengthen theoretical knowledge and effectively organize independent work. If the student fails the test or task contained in the video, he is not allowed to go to the next part of the video, and he is given the opportunity to work with the fragment of the previous part of the video and relearn the material. Videos of this type increase the student's ability to work with information independent

1. Harmon (Accordion)

Accordion

Create vertically stacked expandable items

To the students displayed the text the amount reduce enable will give . Theirs themselves how information in more detail to learn determine and the title click with to open can _ Additional information get for is a wonderful element .

2. Images merge (Agamotto)

Each other on top of it top to layers smooth variable images sequence collect _

Agamotto

Create a sequence of images that gradually

"Zoom" allows you to create beautiful transitions between the text and images.

3. Arithmetic quiz (Arithmetic Quiz)

Timed mini-tests for arithmetic operations.

Arithmetic Quiz

Create time-based arithmetic quizzes

These mini-tests are based on simple arithmetic operations: addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. Questions are randomly generated based on selected arithmetic operations. When creating a quiz, it is enough to specify the type of arithmetic operation and the duration of the quiz. Users can track the score of correct answers and time taken to solve.

4. Recording audio from the microphone get

Audio Recorder

Create an audio recording

Your voice writing get and him immediately execution reach or later on use to WAV file for download enable will give . It's open questions and language courses for great content type _

5. One component inside one several H5P materials placement (Column)

yourself created in materials combined content Create possibility _

Column

Column layout for H5P Content

In the same training material, you can use other H5P materials to create training your grouping can _

6. Presentation (Course Presentation)

Slide presentations can be created with multimedia elements such as quizzes, quizzes, multiple choice questions or interactive videos.

Course Presentation

Create a presentation
with interactive slides

A student one how many from the slides learning object understand and in the presentation one of time in itself himself himself check can _ The content of the slides is easily edited using the visual text editor (WYSIWYG). But the use of the "Presentation" component is not limited to this. You can replace the slide guide with any image or object and create an educational mini-game.

7. Communication cards

A familiar tool for quickly memorizing words, phrases or sentences.

Dialog Cards

Create text-based
turning cards

On the front of the card there is a hint of a word or phrase - in the form of a sound file and/or image. By turning over the card, the student reveals the corresponding word or phrase. It's a good way to learn the language, memorize facts, historical events, formulas and anything else your heart desires.

8. Take drag and drop

Text and pictures walkable elements as using and driving take to throw options Create can _

Drag and Drop

Create drag and drop tasks with images

Allows the student to connect two or more elements and visualize logical connections. The drag and drop component supports combinations for transferring response options: one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many . If you want to complicate the task, there is also the possibility of using other types of H5P content:

- Presentation (Course presentation)
- Interactive video (Interactive video)
- Quiz (Question set)
- Multi-component placement H5P (Column)

9. Essay (Essay)

Essays written by students are checked for keywords previously identified by the author.

Essay

Create essay with instant feedback

One how many the key word options to students written the text quality according to opinion - opinions present in reaching flexibility provides . This type of content does not replace the manual grading of the entire essay by teachers, but it makes the process much easier.

10. Find the desired point-objects in the image by clicking the mouse (Find Multiple Hotspots, , Find the Hotspot)

Can be used for questions where students need to find all the correct dot objects in the picture/pictures.

Find Multiple Hots...

Create many hotspots
for users to find

After clicking, students receive immediate feedback: whether the object was marked correctly and why. It can be used to search for a single object or a whole group - for example, find all devices, systems or network elements . In the settings, the author chooses how many correct points - objects - the student should find before calculating the question .

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